

Revealing Nuances of Non-State Actors in Global Governance and World Politics.

Abstract

In recent years, Non-State Actors (NSAs) have become a crux of the international system, with their tentacles cutting across borders, thereby influencing global governance and world politics.

While there have been extensive studies on non-state actors and its scope has grown to an extent that scholars can no longer ignore their role in international relations, less attention has been given to the relationship between Non-State Actors, Global Governance and World Politics.

In this light, we examine their relationship in this essay.

We do so by raising a plethora of questions which will justify their relationship. These questions are;

What constitutes non-state actors as well as their role in international relations?

Why have non-state actors gained prominence in the affairs of the global arena?

How does their actions impact on global governance and world politics?

What is the fate of state as actors in this regard?

This essay offers an analytic framework in answering these questions.

While noting an increasing level of engagement of non-state actors, I argue that no mapping of the landscape of global governance would be complete without locating the role played by them in global governance and world politics.

Keywords: Transnational Relations, Non-State Actors, Globalization, Global Governance, World Politics.

Introduction

When world politics is discussed by academics, diplomats, politicians and policy makers, it is usually in terms of the diplomatic relations of states, with minuscule details of the activities of non-state actors in world politics. This view of world politics is state-centric. A state-centric view of world politics emphasizes the ability of governments to represent the broad interests of their citizens and equally to control the actions of groups within the nation-state (Nau, 2016, p.45)

The state-centric perspective draws its justification from the 1648 Westphalia Treaty, which established the basis for all the states, irrespective of size, to participate in international relations as equals. In the light of this, ordinarily, it would have been out of place to consider other actors outside of states as influencers of global politics.

However, one of the most prominent features of world politics in the second half of the twentieth century is the significant increase in numbers and importance of non-state actors. Traditionally in world politics, power and authority are considered to rest with nation-states (Bieler, Higgs, & Underhill, 2011, pp. 2-3). This means that since the post-second world war, non-state actors have risen to become actors in the global arena and impacting world politics.

Nation-states are principal actors on the global stage, but they are not the only actors exerting influence, non-state actors are spreading their tentacles across borders to influence international relations.

Theoretical Framework

As regarding the theoretical framework of this discourse, power is central, power in this sense refers to transnational power. For literatures on Non-State Actors, one theme is central, their power and influence and the impact they make on world politics. They have moved from invisible players to influential players with the advent of globalization. All these come down to power.

While non state actors often lack traditional forms of political power/authority, there are alternative sources of power. The key skills and resources that non-state actors possess have been identified as deriving from their intellectual, political and financial bases (Gulbrandsen & Andersen, 2004, p. 58)

The different sources of non-state actor power are believed to include knowledge and information (Betsil & Corell, 2008; Keck & Sikkink, 1999); economic resources and position in the global economy (Falkner, 2010; Levy & Newell, 2000; Newell, 2000); organizational capacity, transnational networking and mobilization capacity (Falkner, 2010) and legitimacy (Gough & Shackley, 2001).

Therefore, we can identify a number of power sources and based on (Keck & Sikkink, 1999, p. 95) and (Bostrom & Tamm Hallström, 2010, p. 43), we build various typology of power sources used by non-state actors to gain authority in global governance.

What are Non-State Actors?

Non-State Actors (NSAs) are all those actors that are not representatives of states, yet, they operate at the international level and are potentially relevant to international relations (Arts et al; 2001; Furtak, 1997; Higgot et al; 2000). This simply means that they are not states, yet operative at the international level and relevant to international relations.

Relevant to international relations? One might ask. According to (Morss, 1991), an indicator of relevancy refers to the size, constituency, formal recognition and political impact of non-state actors in order to decide whether they are relevant global players or not. All these are inherent in the configuration of NSAs.

There are various groups of NSAs, they include Transnational Advocacy Networks, Multinational Corporations (MNCs)/ Transnational Corporations (TNCs), Transnational Diaspora Communities, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), International Non-Governmental Organizations (IGOs).

Some argue that IGOs such as UN, NATO and the WTO are not NSAs, because they established by states and instrumental to state interests (Furtak, 1997).

Others argue that IGOs are autonomous from states, given their expertise, independent personnel and ties to NGOs (Archer, 1983; Reinalda, 2001; Reinalda & Verbeek, 1998).

According to (Thompson-Feraru, 1974), NGOs are non-profit that seek to influence outcomes in international politics. Examples are Oxfam International, Greenpeace International, Pax Christi, among others.

NGOs maximizes their political impact, thus furthering public aims (Furtak, 1997; Reinalda 2001)

TNCs is another NSA category that some might confuse with MNCs, but (Higgots et al; 2000), distinguished between the both, MNCs replicate their activities in a number of region to avoid the risk of trade blocs and TNCs strive for a worldwide intra-firm division of labour.

What Does Influence of Non-State Actors on Global Governance Mean? Can the World be Governed?

What do we mean by global governance? Global governance refers to the collective efforts undertaken to identify, understand and address world wide problems that go beyond the problem solving capacities of states (Weiss Thakur, 2010). These global problems include climate change, pandemics, cyber-threats, terrorism , amongst others.

One might ask, how can the world be governed? Especially since there are unresolved global problems and not enough political structures established for problem solving, coupled with the need for nation-states to attend to their domestic issues. Answers are nurtured from the influence and interventions of non-state actors, which includes NGOs, TNCs, MNCs to address these trans-boundary problems, thereby influencing global governance.

Multinational Corporations vis-à-vis World Politics

Prior to the nineteenth century, world politics was majorly an interplay of states. However, in recent times, world politics is inclusive of non-state actors shaping the international scene. Multinational corporations have grown dramatically in scope and influence since the second world war (Kegley & Raymond, 2010, p. 164). They are companies based in one state with affiliate branches or subsidiaries operating in other states (Goldstein & Pevehouse, 2012, p. 341). The immense wealth of the largest multinational corporations gives them considerable influence in world politics (Navareth & Venables, 2006, p.18). They have the ability to make decisions on many issues over which national political leaders have little control over (Kegley & Raymond, 2010).

Examples of these multinational corporations and their influence are, Google's engagement with EU regulations, Huawei's political support for China, Exxon's influence in energy markets. Two prominent critics, US Senators Olympia Snowe and Jay Rockefeller wrote to the head of Exxon Mobil, accusing the corporation of supporting action groups who are producing questionable data that denies the reality of global warming (Rourke, 2008). This affirms the influence of multinational corporations in world politics and global governance.

Transnational Advocacy Networks and World Politics

According to (D'Anier, 2010, p. 357), among the many different non-state actors, transnational advocacy networks have begun to play a role of growing importance in world politics and in particular countries.

Following the view of (Boissevain & Mitchel, 1973), transnational advocacy networks, includes relevant actors working internationally on an issue, bound by shared values, a common discourse and desire for exchange of information and service.

Information is instrumental in world politics. By mobilizing information in support of a cause, they change the nature of international policy and practice (Rosenau, 1990, p.12). These advocacy networks have influenced international policy-making.

For example, during the 1970s and 1980s, many states decided for the first time on the promotion of human rights in other countries was a legitimate foreign policy goal, the decision came in part from interaction with an emerging global human rights network (Becker, 2012, p. 45). Therefore, advocacy networks play a compelling role in world politics.

Violent Non-State Actors and World Politics

They are non-state armed groups, that resort to organized violence as a tool to achieve their goals (Mulaj, 2010, p. 3). Their actions on world politics create a threat-like folder of influence. Most of them are agitators of succession and tend to call themselves freedom fighters. Examples are Liberation Tigers of Tamil Eelam (LTTE), the Irish Republican Army (IRA).

According to (Mandel, 2013), violent non-state actors have acquired significant importance in contemporary world politics. Their actions and quest for power continually affects the power politics on the global arena.

Transnational Diaspora Communities in World Politics

Diasporas are influential non-state actors, whose actions cut across borders. Diaspora politics involves the inclusion of homeland politics into host country, providing external dimension and acting as a resource for political counterparts (Smith, 1991).

For example, the 1991 revolution in China was primarily financed by overseas Chinese (Esman, 1986). It was the Czech diaspora that initiated the establishment of Czechoslovakia after the First World War (Akzim, 1964, p. 248). The attempt of the African diaspora in the United States to take effective measure against South Africa due to its racist policies (Leanne, 1995, pp. 25-26).

Their goals are attainable because their homeland government will want to protect the image of the country in the international scene and these government are seeking legitimacy and acceptance. This waters the ground for influence of these diasporas on the international plane.

Conclusion

So we can assert that, although states are the principal actors in the global scene, they are not the only dominant actors.

An understanding of the place of non-state actors is integral in embracing the new realities of modern international politics.

We are not certain of the dynamics of world politics and global governance, but we are aware of the ever increasing role of non-state actors on the global arena, thereby exerting influence.

In whatever form their influence exists, be it positive forms of influence by multinational corporations, diaspora communities, transnational advocacy networks or violence-like forms of influence by violent non-state actors, the only constant is that they are capable of shaping the affairs of the international system.

Non-State Actors are not only part of the new world, they also influence the order of the new world.

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